

Test Cells to Generate Reference Partial Discharge Series

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Abstract — This paper describes the design and characterization of test cells developed to generate a reference data bank of partial discharge (PD) series. The reference PD signals reproduced in these cells are useful for the evaluation of AC and DC PD diagnosis instruments. Technical functionalities such as PD sensitivity, PD clustering and PD source recognition can be checked using these test cells. A testing procedure to detect the existence of a specific defect in HVDC installations is proposed. This work is part of a task of the European co-funded project on metrology 15NRM02-UHV-EMPIR, which is focused in the achievement of valuable results for the IEC/CENELEC standardization.

Index Terms — Partial discharges, insulation testing, fault diagnosis, performance evaluation, pattern analysis, pattern clustering.

I. INTRODUCTION

PD measurements performed in HV laboratories according to IEC 60270 [1] have traditionally served to verify the quality of high voltage material, machines and apparatus. Currently expertise technicians perform on-site PD measurements to check the insulation condition of MV and HV installations. Both off-line and on-line PD measurements are performed using different technologies, methods and criteria. Although the same diagnosis conclusion should be achieved, in practice, significant discrepancies arise when different approaches are applied. These discrepancies can be justified mainly by the absence of a procedure for the verification of the technical performances of PD diagnosis instruments. Additional difficulties arise when HVDC PD diagnostics are required, due to the particular behavior of many insulation media which are affected by polarization effects. The CIGRE working group D1.63 is researching in this field and collecting technical background of the state of the art about PD testing in HVDC installations. Besides, more effort regarding the improvement of electromagnetic methods for AC and DC on-site PD measurements are needed to contribute with the recent technical specification IEC 62478 [2].

II. OVERVIEW OF THE STATE OF THE ART

Many test cells have been developed by different authors to analyze the PD behavior in insulation defects of different materials, liquids and gases when AC or DC high voltages are applied [3] and [4].

The presence of defects in dielectrics, such as cavity in a solid insulation, degradation of isolated surfaces, floating metal parts, corona, false contacts, etc. involves the inception

of PD pulses that when they are measured are commonly visualized in characteristic PD patterns. The phase resolved PD (PRPD) patterns obtained for AC voltages grids are very useful for the diagnosis of the insulation condition. However, in HVDC grids, only patterns related with the sequence of pulses of the PD series (amplitudes and time interval between consecutive PD pulses) are available. Thus, when HVDC measurements are carried out, clustering tools to separate different PD sources are really indispensable for the separated analysis of each PD series. Test cells representing real defects are needed for the generation of reference PD pulse series, in order to evaluate the efficiency of pulses clustering techniques.

III. DESIGN OF THE PD TEST CELLS

A. General considerations

The most important requirement to be satisfied by a test cell to generate reference PD series is to ensure that it generates only one PD source in the required operation conditions (voltage, temperature, pressure and humidity ranges). In addition, negligible or well-known aging conditions of the defect made in the test cell are required. Furthermore, if several test cells must operate in the same verification test generating PD pulses, for instance to verify the PD clustering capability of a PD diagnosis instrument, all the test cells must generate representative PD patterns in a common voltage range in which the test voltage is applied. The test cells presented in this research were characterized by aging tests of more than 50 hours in order to verify that their physical features and behavior remain stable at least over this time. In any case, after 10 hours in operation, it is suggested to change the PE test sample by another PE sample.

B. Inception voltage in the electrode of the test cells

The inception voltage U_i for an electrical configuration is given by the following equation:

$$U_i = E_{dh} \cdot s \cdot \eta \quad (1)$$

where

U_i is the inception voltage.

s the gap distance.

η the inhomogeneity coefficient, and

E_{dh} the breakdown electrical field for quasi-homogenous field in air, that is given by the empirical formula:

$$E_{dh} = 23 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{R}}\right) \quad (2)$$

where, R , is the curvature radius of the electrode expressed in cm to get the electrical field expressed in kV/cm.

Rod electrodes with a semi-spherical end are used to generate corona, cavity and surface PD pulses (see the upper row of Fig. 1). For fixed gap distances, s , well-known dielectric media and electrode configurations, and controlled operating conditions (temperature, pressure and humidity), the inception voltage can be selected by choosing an appropriate curvature radius of the rod electrode. The maximum electrical field in each test cell is calculated using the finite element software FEMM, which is applied to the test cell that has a revolution geometry. The PD pulses generated in the rod electrode are directly acquired by a UHF recorder (1GHz of bandwidth and 5 GS/s of sampling rate). The waveform of the pulses measured in each test cell is shown in the second row of Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. First row: Graphical output of electrical field concentration in the test cells calculated by means of FEMM. Second row: PD pulse waveforms measured with a UHF recorder under HVDC(-).

C. Characterization. Time response

The time response of each test cell (see Fig. 2) was determined to estimate the influence of the electrode configuration on the PD pulse waveform, analyzing the partial response time, the overshoot and the stabilization time.

Fig. 2. a) Testing setup for the time response measurement, b) Time response of the cavity test cell: $T_{\alpha}=1.1\text{ns}$, $T_N<0.1\text{ns}$ $\beta=0.75$, $t_s=6\text{ns}$.

IV. RESULTS OF PD SERIES

Fig. 3 and 4 show some results of PD series generated with three test cells (cavity, surface and corona). The kind of high voltage applied (AC or DC) has a crucial influence on the

expected PD behavior of the PD series, especially for the cavity test cell. For example when 20 kV DC negative polarity is applied to the cavity PE test cell, the average time interval between two consecutive PD pulses is around 2000 times greater (2 s) than the time obtained for HVAC (1 ms).

Fig. 3. Cavity defect: a) PD series at four HVDC (-) levels: 14 kV, 16 kV, 18 kV and 20 kV b) PRPD pattern for AC 15 kV_{rms}.

Fig. 4. a) Charge amplitudes for AC corona using different rod radius 0.25 mm, 0.5 mm, 1 mm and 2 mm b) PD series at four HVDC (-) levels: 5 kV, 7 kV, 9 kV and 11 kV.

The corona test cell ($r=1\text{mm}$) can be used as a stable PD source for a wide voltage range in AC voltage (see Fig.4a). The surface test cell can be used as a charge source depending on the voltage level. The three cells can generate reference PD series to be used for the verification of functional capabilities of PD diagnosis instruments.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The developed test cells of different defects (corona, cavity and surface) enable to check the functional performances of commercial PD diagnosis instruments used for HVAC and HVDC grids. For every specific rod radius considered in the test cell, if the atmospheric conditions remain constant, the corona discharges generated present a constant charge value in a significant range of voltages.

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